

Extra Input Helper Functions

Snakemake Hackathon 2025 - Report

1 Extra Input Helper Functions

1.1 Author

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1.2 Description

This work item aims at adding several new helper functions.

1.2.1 Summary of Enhancements

The release described here adds several new input functions to Snakemake:

- **Input File Sizes:** Before, Snakemake only provided functions to return the total size of the input files in bytes (`size()`) and megabytes (`size_mb()`). Here we expand these functions to also return the sizes of each input file (`size_files_*`) as well as in kilobytes (kb) and gigabytes (gb).
- **Parse Input Files:** Added function to parse input files and return its content through a callable (`parse_input()`). Apart from that, we also provide a callable to search for a given file name in a md5 checksum file and return its checksum (`extract_checksum()`).

1.2.2 Impact

The new input functions make it easier for the user to perform several common input operations, as well as improving code readability and reducing the probability of bugs. For example, the functions `parse_input()` and `extract_checksum()` can be usefull when downloading a file and its md5sum file from the internet:

rule a:

```
input:
    checksum=storage.http("https://path/to/file.md5"),
output:
    tsv="file.tsv",
params:
    url="https://path/to/file.tsv",
    checksum=parse_input(input.checksum, parser=extract_checksum, file="file.tsv")
shell:
    "aria2c --checksum md5={params.checksum} --out {output.tsv} {params.url}; "
```

1.3 Associated Project Workitem

- [PR 2424 - feat: Add extra input size properties](#)
- [PR 2918 - feat: add helper functions to parse input files](#)

1.4 Acknowledgement

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